

ROLE OF SKILL INDIA MISSION FOR ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Globalization, knowledge and competition have increased the need of highly skilled workforce in both the developing and developed nations accelerating their growth rate towards higher flight. India is one of the fastest growing economy in the world, blessed with huge percentage of youth that constitute India's population but most of youth of India are not fully skilled as per requirement of industry and this is a major hurdle in India's growth. Skill and knowledge are the key factors in order to overcome such hurdle and helping India to embark on road of endless growth. For this skill development is a necessity, as it is not helps in youth of the country to acquire necessary skills but also helps in economic development of a country. The present paper attempts to study the present skill capacity, skill development programme, challenges of skill India programme, current status of skill India programme, step taken by the Govt. etc. The paper reviews the current state of education policy, skill development programme, employment opportunities in skill sector, and considers the challenges faced by India's skills development system. The vision Skill India Mission is inclusive growth in area of enhance electronic services, enhance manufacturing, innovation and development of new product and increase job opportunities for the youth of the country. This research work has been done on the basis of secondary data and literature. The secondary data has been collected from different sources like research article, research book, government reports, surveys and website, publication of the various articles etc.

Keywords: - Skill Development, Economic Development, Youth, Employment

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INTRODUCTION

The Skill India Mission launched in July 2015 by the Government of India with a vision to developed for skill of workforce through India which will emphasize the overall efforts so that the economy can grow by the exponential growth rate and come out from the crisis of poverty and unemployment. Human capital is a very significant asset of the nation. The country which have utilised human capital properly have become developed and which types of country they are not utilised properly there human resource has remained underdeveloped economy. In current situation India is a fastest growing economy in the world. But less skill human resources is one of the key challenges of Indian economy. The primary objective of Skill India is to create a skilled and productive workforce that can contribute to the growth and development of the nation. Skill India promotes entrepreneurship and support the development of small and medium enterprises by equipping individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge. It enhance the employability of the Indian workforce and make them more competitive in the global job market. Under the Skill India initiatives, the Government of India has taken a number of initiatives and project to transform and improve governance, services and connectivity for the nation. Some of the key initiatives are PMKVY, PM YUVA Yojna, Skill Loan Scheme, Jan Sikshan Sansthan, SANKALP Scheme, UDAAN etc. Skill India programme involved putting in place curriculum-based skill training programme, where learners would receive certificate and endorsements from learning facilities that were well-known in the industry. Skill India Mission including skill-based learning in the school

curriculum and fostering both long-term and short term possibilities for Skill training and employment.

20 Skill India is today a major project that involves every segment of the Indian society local and foreign companies and Governments. Skill India program will equip and train the nation's massive, enviable workforce with employable skills and knowledge. This programme will help them contribute substantially to India's industrialization and economic boom. Over 400 million women and men in the country will be trained in various industrial and trade skill by the year-2022. Every ministry of the Government of India is involved in the massive skill India program billed as the world's largest initiative to train manpower in a single country or geographic location. Skill India program will help reduce dependence on urban and semi urban Jobs. It will provide ample work and business avenues in rural India too. Several foreign countries including UK, US, Israel, Germany and France have signed UP skill India partners to train Indians in specific skill.

NSDC (National Skill Development Corporation) is a unique model created by the GOI which is based on 3 pillars like Create, Fund, Enable. The main objective of government through this type of model is create large, quality vocational training institutes and creation and sustainability of support system required for skill development. It is also helpful to developed necessary framework to upgrade skills to International standards, enhancing, supporting and coordinating with private sectors for skill development initiatives through appropriate PPP (Public Private Partnership) models.

PMKVY (Pradhan Mantri Koshal Vikas Yojna) is a flagship programme under NSDC with the objective of allowing huge number of youth to take up and upgrade their skill in the field of like Industrial Training, Computer Knowledge which would help them getting job securing their livelihood. Key components of this scheme includes such as Rozgar Mela, Short Term Training, Automobile Training, Electrical Training, Accounting Programme, Beautician Training, Mobile repairing Training etc.

SANKALP (Skills Acquisition and Knowledge Awareness for Livelihood Promotion) project aims to implement the mandate of the National Skill Development Mission (NSDM), which was launched on 15th July by Ministry of Skill Development & Entrepreneurship Department. The main objectives of the project include strengthening institutional mechanisms at both national and state level, building a pool of quality trainers and assessors, creating convergence among all skill training activities at the state level, establishing robust monitoring and evaluation system for skill programme.

Trained Persons Under Skill Development Initiative in India -2022

Ministries/Organisation/Department	Target/Projected No. of Trained Persons (In Million)
National Skill Development Corporation	150
Labour and Employment	100
HRD Higher Education HRD Vocational Education	50
Transport	30
Rural Development	20
Agriculture	20

Construction Industry Development Council (Under Planning Commission)	20
Urban Development	15
Micro Small Medium Enterprises	15
Power Petroleum Etc.	15
Textiles	10
Health and Family Welfare	10
Women and Child Welfare	10
Department of Information Technology	10
Finance/Insurance/Banking	10
Consumer Affairs	10
Department of Heavy Industry	10
Chemicals and Fertilizers	5
Overseas Indian Affairs	5
Social Justice and Empowerment	5
Food Processing Industry	5
Tourism	5
Total	530

Source:-National Skill Development Policy Ministry of Labour Government of India

In this table, at present 17 ministries of Government of India are undertaking skill development initiatives with a collective target of developing 530 million skilled people by 2022. It is positive indicator of Indian economy.

Incremental Skilled Manpower Requirement in India-2022

Industries/Sectors	Skilled Manpower Requirement (In Million)
Building and Construction Industry	33
Real Estate Service	14
Gem and Jewellery	4.6
Lear and Lear Goods	4.6
Organised Retails	17.3
Textiles and Clothing	26.2
Electronic and IT Hardware	3.3
Auto and Auto Components	35
IT and ITES	5.3
Banking Finance Services and Insurance	4.2
Furniture and Furnishing	3.4
Infrastructure Structure	103
Tourism and Hospitality Services	3.6
Construction Material and Building	1.4

Chemicals and Pharmaceuticals	1.9
Food Processing	9.3
Healthcare	12.7
Transport and Logistic	17.7
Media and Entertainment	3
Education and Skill Development Services	5.8
Select Informal Employment Sectors(Domestic Help Beauticians Facility Management Security Guards)	37.6
Total Incremental Requirement	347

Sources: National Skill Development Corporation Government of India

According to a research Boston Consulting Group it is estimated that by 2020 India had a surplus of active population (in working age 15-59 years)- about 60% of total population. By 2026 around 64% of population of India is expected to be in category of active population (age bracket of 15-59 years) with merely 13% aged above 60 years. Such increasing percentage of active population will provide India opportunities to improve labour productivity boost production and within next 10-15 years position itself among developed country of world.

Formal Skill Training of India Compared to Developed Countries

Country	Korea	Japan	Germany	UK	USA	India
Formal Skill Training	96%	80%	75%	68%	52%	2.3%

India has a big challenge ahead as it is estimated that only 2.3% of the total workforce in India has undergone formal skill training as compared to 96% in Korea, 80% in Japan, 75% in Germany, 68% in UK and 52% in USA.

FEATURES OF SKILL INDIA

Following of the features are

1. Train Indian citizens of all ages, especially youth, to get employment or established their own MSMES in sector like Automobile, electricity, village industry, and many more.
2. Skill India will also focus on core sector like such as. Construction, gems and Jewellery, banking finance, transport and tourism and entrepreneurship.
3. Training provided to enrolled Indian citizens will conform to international standards. There will be creating a good business environment in Indian industrialisation and make India a skilled country in the world.
4. Course offered under skill India consider various factors such as age geographical location native language and financial status. Skill India program trains people in communication, management, entrepreneurial and social skills, among other.
5. Provide training, technical and financial support for various trades including leather, healthcare workers, fashion designers khadi and handloom and other.
6. Training provided by the skill India program is expected to fulfil the demand for skilled manpower.

7. Skill India also looks at training Indians for employment in industrialized country of the world.

SKILL INDIA PROGRAMME COVERS FOLLOWING SECTORS

Agriculture:- including floriculture, horticulture and all related branches.

Beauty and Wellness:- In this section skill are provided to body and beauty treatments to all section of the Indian society.

Banking, finance, stock and Insurance:- In this section skills are provided to get employment in the financial sectors of India. These types of skill also promote entrepreneurship.

Capital Goods:- In this section training are provided to people on all aspect of design, development, manufacture and of capital Goods such as machinery and equipment for home, office and industry.

Construction:- In this section skill are provided to people for design to construction of all civil, industrial and military infrastructures. Such as buildings and complexes, bridges and subways among other.

Electronics:- In this section skill are provided for designing manufacture and maintenance of vital electronic equipment for home, office, industry.

IMPACT OF SKILL INDIA

There are some impacts of Skill India which are as follows:-

1. Impact on agriculture sector – The government will shift from e- governance to m – governance that is mobile governance. Farmers can access all kind of information through their mobile phone as when required which will boost of agriculture sector.
2. Impact on Indian Economy – Skill India can play a key role in Macro Economic factors such as GDP Growth, Employment generation, Skilled Labour Productivity growth in number of businesses and revenue leakage for the government. It is also helpful in Macro Economic factor such as increase the demand of product to the costumer, price discrimination of the product, easy to access a good supply chain to the suppliers etc.
3. Impact on Environment -The major changes in the technology space has not only brought changes to the economic system but is contributing to the environment changes. The next generation technologies are helping in lowering the carbon footprint by reducing fuel consumption, waste management, greener management, greener workplaces and thus leading to a greener ecosystem.
4. Impact on social sector- Modern ICT makes it easier for people to obtain access to service may be highly useful as a complementary channel to public service delivery apart from creation of entirely new services. The success of the Skill India project not the benefits of the government only but also the benefits of all round support from the all citizen and other stake holder of the nation.
5. Impact on Technology – Technology infrastructure is play a key role for economic development. Without a proper skill infrastructure can not developed a nation. Skill India provide a framework to all round development a nation such as E-Education, E-Health, E-Governance, E-Business etc.
6. Impact of Education and Skill Development- Skill India provide a opportunities to access the employment opportunities in the field of like education, Infrastructure,

banking, insurance, agriculture, heavy industry, transport etc. It is very difficult to provide education and skill development without digital infrastructure whole of the nation. Digital platform like SWAYAM and E-Learning initiative have expanded access to quality and skill development opportunities. It has enabled remote learning, making education more easy available and accessible to all.

7. Start-ups and Innovation:-start-up India campaign is an effective action plan which has intent to promote ventures to increase entrepreneurship and encourage start ups with job creation. Start-up India is a revolutionary scheme that has been started to help the people who wish to start their own business.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of literature is the base of any research work. without review of literature a researcher cannot plan for further research on any topic and area. After a deep study and review of contemporary literature a researcher becomes able to set of his research objectives and needs of research. The work related to the study may support or conflict with present results. A number of research paper and articles provide a detailed knowledge about the role of Skill India and the implications of this project in India.

In his research paper, there is a scope of international collaboration and assistance in India's skill development initiative at almost all levels including for creating awareness and capabilities setting standards improving quality as well as providing opportunities.

Anantwar Shivai Pradip and V.B. Dakora, In his research paper discussed that Skill and Knowledge are the driving forces of the economic growth and social development of any country they have become even more important given the increasing space of globalisation and technological changes provide the both challenges that is taking place in the world. Countries with higher and better level of skill adjust more effectively to the challenges and opportunities of globalisation.

Sulochana. M. (2018) has expressed views in his research paper that, to make India internationally competitive and to boost its economic growth further, a skilled youth is essential. It become increasingly important for it to focus on achievement of the skills and these skills have to be relevant to the emerging economic environment. For transforming its demographic dividend, an efficient skill development system is the need of the hour.

OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

1. To study about the awareness of Skill India Mission.
2. To know about the challenges and opportunities of Skill India Mission.
3. To examine about the role of Skill India Mission in the context of economic development.
4. To study about the future prospects of the Skill India Mission.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research work has been done on the basis of secondary data and literature. Major aims of this paper to analysis the skill development initiative in India. The secondary data has been collected from Reports of skill India ministry, Skill India website, Skill India Journals, Reports of Government of India and various website.

NEED OF THE STUDY

Skill infrastructure is the back bone of economic development. Skill India initiative has a capacity to developed Skill infrastructure in the country. There are many programme launched by the government to support Skill India. But Skill India specially targeted to develop human Skill for the youth of the country. It has a capacity to generate more employment opportunities, create a Skilled Infrastructure base, development of productive quality of Indian product. Skill India Programme plays a very important role for the growth of nation like primary sector, secondary sector and service sector of the economy.

NEED OF SKILL INDIA MISSION

India is a youth populated country in the world. With the support of skill India initiatives unemployment hurdle can be solved. Unemployment is a big challenge of Indian economy. Workforce who is skilled is crucial for success of recently launched mission by country like Make in India, Digital India, Swach Bharat Abhiyan, Smart city Yojna, Sagarmal Project and many more.

SKILL INDIA AND JOB CREATION AT NATIONAL LEVEL

One of the vital aims of Make in India campaign is to enhance skills of the human resources to fulfill the requirement of skilled man power in the manufacturing sector. Skilled workforce in India is about 2% which is very low compared to China 47%, Japan 80%, and South Korea 96%. Workforces of India were facing lack of proper skills. This was a main cause of unemployment and industries were facing of scarcity of skilled man power. According to India Skills Report 2015, only 37.22% of surveyed people were found employable out of which 37.88% were female and 34.26% were male. Labor productivity of India was found of low productivity and India ranked last among 60 countries in labor productivity.

Skilled Human Resource is an important factor to encourage the investors. For the purpose of skill development, National Skill Development Mission (NSDM) is launched by the government of India in 2015 just after one year of launching of Make in India. Skill India aims to trained more than 30 crore people in India in different skills by 2022 to fulfill the needs of workforce for the manufacturing sectors. National Skill Development Corporation of India (NSDCI) is the nodal body of skill India mission. Skill Development helps in mitigate poverty, utilize demographic dividend, socio-economic improvement of under privileged sectors and achieve economic growth, reduce social challenges and economic inclusion.

India has entered into partnership with U.K. 11 British Companies are supporting for Skill Development in India. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikash Yojana, Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship and Rural India Skill have been playing a very vital role in skill development of the urban as well as rural people.

The Ministry of Skill Development has assessed an incremental human resource requirement across 24 manufacturing sectors as 109.73 million by 2022. The National Skill Development Policy (2009) has set a target of skilling 500 million people by 2022. The National Skill Development Corporation (NSDC) was mandated to skill 150 million, while the Directorate General of Employment and Training (DGET), under the Ministry of Labor and Employment was to skill 100 million. Currently, over 70 skill development schemes across various sectors are being implemented by over 20 Central Ministries /Departments.

Table- presented data of target for skill development and actually persons skilled by various ministries. Achievements of skill development is up to 104%. It is clear from the data that the

progress of skill development is very good and it may be said government is paying good attention in this direction.

Schemes Implemented by Various Ministries

Year	Target (in lakhs)	Persons Skilled (in lakhs)	Achievement
2011-12	46.53	45.58	98%
2012-13	72.51	51.88	72%
2013-14	73.42	76.37	104%
2014-15	105.07	51.50*	49%

Source: Lok Sabha Questions, *up to February, 2015

Person Trained by National Skill Development Corporation (NSDC) (in lakhs)

Source: Lok Sabha Questions, *up to February, 2015

As per above diagram- total 50.34 lakh persons have trained by NSDC during period 2010-11 to 2014-15 out of them 15.31 lakh have placed. It reveals the role of NSDC in skill development as well as their placement is remarkable.

CHALLENGES OF SKILL INDIA

Following of the challenges are faced in the successful implementation of Skill India Mission-

Lake of knowledge to Skill Education- Most of the people of the country is not aware of skill India Mission. Lower literacy rate is a very big issue of Indian economy. Therefore there is big problem to achieve the aims of Skill India mission.

High cost – Skill India programme is a huge programme of GOI. It included many types of skilled programme like. It is a new programme of GOI and proper implementation of this programme is a challenging task of the government. It also a high cost programme.

Financial and technical issues- India is still a developing country. For a plan like this initiative, huge financial resources are required and the country somehow lacks in that area. It requires financial assistance from other sources. Technical issues like internet services,

firewalls, filters, anti-virus software's, protection from hackers, buffering are some of the technical issues the country has to face.

Lack of computer knowledge- Computer knowledge is one of the basic requirements in current time. All types of Skill programme is generally provided through computer. Many types of Skill programme like Accounting Knowledge, Hotel Management course, Training programme, Software knowledge programme, Cyber safety training and many more is based on computer training programme. Lack of computer knowledge is a challenging task to proper implementation of the programme.

Attitude of citizens as well as government personnel- For successful implementation of the programme, a wholesome effort is required of both the citizens and the government personnel. Moreover, the older generation is set in their way and find the traditional methods of doing things easy and convenient. Indian political power structure lack of inter-departmental coordination add to the problem.

Training need issue- Skill India programme is a skilled based training programme. There is a big challenge to provide a world class skill training for the people. It is a challenging task to trained people in working place because people are belongs to different geographical and different qualification. Most of the population lack the basic qualification required for the skilled programme.

FINDING OF STUDY

Skill India is a skill development programme of youth of the country. Social sector has contributed a significant role in the development of Indian economy. Social sector such as education, healthcare, and banking are unable to reach out to the citizens due to obstructions and limitation such as middleman, illiteracy, poverty, lack of funds, living locality and investment. Skill India has provided new job opportunities in the field like education sector, banking sector, internet sector, electronic sector, automobile sector, etc.

Skill India has a capacity to provide a global reorganisation of Indian Economy through the development of skill knowledge of the youth. .

Skill India programme creating great awareness about growing and development of Indian economy in the field of infrastructure, industrial Development, Electronic Sector, Railways etc. Skill India programme creates new opportunities for multiple sectors such as in field of like E-Education, E-Banking, E-Commerce, E-Health, Marketing Sector etc.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Skill India is a dream project of the Modi Government were many of the programme are ongoing process and some of the are yet to start in future time. Necessary design, reengineering and redesign in the field of Skill Development are needed for the successful implementation of the project. Skill India is a huge campaign which will take long period for giving result and also a specific data are not available. The researcher has observed that presently this campaign is in progress and now we will have to wait for get the outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Skill India is no more just limited opportunities to the domestic market but also opportunities of countries across the world to promote cross geographical exposure and opportunities in the international market. Skills help people improve their socioeconomic status, which boost social development. As people develop marketable skills, they can get better paying jobs, breaking the cycle of poverty and improving communities. A skilled workforce boosts the economy. Skills development ensures that people can contribute across sectors. This boosts

production, innovation, technology development, and efficiency. Skill India programme making Indian enterprises and sectors more competitive compare abroad. It has a capacity to provide a large scale of employment for the youth that will boost the India's economy. It is also helpful to achieve the aims to ensure holistic development of a nation. Skill India mission has improved the performance of the life of people as well on trade. The overall growth and development can be achieved through supporting and enhancing element of the society such as literacy, basic infrastructure, government plans, and overall business environment. A Skilled society connected India which is helpful in improving social and economic condition of the people through development digital infrastructure base from easy to access to basic infrastructure like education, health and financial services. The overall development and growth can be realized through supporting and enhancing elements such as literacy, basic infrastructure, overall business environment, regulatory environment, Government policies, etc.

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